

EXPRESSION IS A WIDESPREAD LITERARY GENRE

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Annotation: Despite the fact that the original philosophy emerged as a practical embodiment of love-pursuit of wisdom, in the framework of modern Western culture it should still be considered as a specific «literary» tradition of knowledge. In such circumstances, the problem of investigating of the existing genres of philosophical literature seems relevant. The article is devoted to the solution of this problem.

Keywords: Philosophy, literature, genre, discourse, creation, knowledge.

Due to the fact that in the modern world any information, any knowledge can become socially significant phenomena only if they are practically implemented in a sign form, in one or another type of writing, we can state that at the moment the attitude to any branch or field of knowledge should be built through the comprehension of its "literary" character (the term "literature" here means "the scope of some specific grammatical practice"). In such a context, philosophy should also be perceived, first of all, as a special "literary", written tradition of knowledge. This inevitability was very well expressed by J.-F. Lyotard, who stated that "after Socrates, to philosophize is to write".

In the case of our appeal to this tradition, we will, among other things, face the need to comprehend the genre affiliation of a huge set of works and texts (the concept of "genre" here should be interpreted as a kind of "form of writing").

Let's try to further explore the possible classification of philosophical genres, that is, written philosophical forms inherent in the Western tradition of philosophizing. In doing so, we will be aware of the following evidence:

1) the concept of "genre" itself, both in its essence and in our perception, is inextricably linked with the idea of the so-called "fiction", therefore some "artistic" contexts for understanding this term cannot be completely eliminated from our study;

2) asking the question about the existing genres of philosophical writing, we thereby also pose the problem of the rhetorical content of philosophy. Traditionally, the significance of this content is reduced to a minimum, however,

considering philosophy as a “literary” phenomenon, we will inevitably face the need to reassess this attitude.

The problem of the species category in literary theory remains open and rather controversial. The place of this concept is not defined - where and how to use it. Very often this category is used as a synonym for the concept of "genre". One of the reasons for this is the fact that the term "genre" comes from the French "genre" and it is customary to translate it as a genus, genre, species. Therefore, the boundary between genre and type is very often leveled, and they are used as synonyms. It is because of this uncertainty that there are many interpretations of the literary division. In one case, it is proposed to single out a genus, species, variety, in another - a genus, genre, variety, or - a genus, species, genre, variety. As you can see, not all variants have the category of species, or it is used in the understanding of "genre". Although the category of the species under its name understands the concept of a broader scale than the genre. Given this fact, as well as a wide variety of literary works, we propose to adhere to the following literary division: genus - species - genre - variety - modification. In this list, the species category occupies the second place, and, accordingly, a criterion that would be common to all genres should be taken into account. Thus, the question arises: “What should be the basis of the category of species ≤”. Some scientists have already tried to answer this question. Therefore, we will consider their concepts using the example of poetry. It is traditional to divide lyrics into civil, philosophical, landscape and love. Such a classification looks like rather concise and inactive system, which does not reflect the entire palette of diversity of poetry. However, there are other views. So G. Pospelov singled out meditative, meditative-pictorial and pictorial lyrics. The researcher noted that meditativeness is the main property of lyrics, since it is present in more or to a lesser degree in any poetry and for many lyrical works is their external form. The peculiarity of the content of meditative lyrics lies in the fact that in it "the public consciousness of the poet turns out to be both an ontological and epistemological subject of knowledge" [7, p. 68]. poetry that tends to go beyond the boundaries of m meditativity into the objective world, G. Pospelov calls meditative-pictorial lyrics. If the subject of knowledge is nature, landscapes, then this is pictorial poetry, which embodies the emotions of the author in its features. In addition to the listed types of lyrics, the literary critic also singled out character and narrative lyrics. For the first, the object of lyrical meditation becomes a person who embodies the “characteristic of social life” [7, p. 151]. For poetry to become narrative, it must have characters, action. G. Pospelov divided the types of lyrics on the basis of different functions of artistic speech. So meditation is an act of verbal expression of thoughts, feelings, descriptive lyrics is a reflection of the events of the external world in statics, narrative is “a verbal reproduction of actions and movements in space and time”

Among modern views on the problem of the genre, the concept of the Ukrainian literary critic N. Kopystyanskaya looks interesting. The concept of "genre" and "genre system" combine "constant and changeable" [4, p. 77]. She proposes to consider the genre in four areas that form a spiral. The first sphere reveals the genre as a constant general literary concept. The second one characterizes the dynamics of the genre in a certain historical epoch, direction, flow. The third sphere reflects the national features of the concept. In the fourth, the content of the genre is concretized, which concerns the individual work of the writer. That is, in the first area, the relationship of "the relative stable principles of organizing all content and formal genre-forming components into a single aesthetic whole" is revealed [4, p. 34]. A genre can be transformed through a change in themes, attitudes towards traditions, a change in ideas about the beautiful, about the subject of art, also through interaction with other genres, types of art, through the influence of genre theories, and this is displayed in the second sphere. The third reveals the originality of the development of the genre in a certain national literature. Here the historical conditions for the development of the people, the nation should be taken into account, and the influence of folklore is also revealed. The fourth sphere reveals the genre through the individual creativity of the author, this sphere is extremely unstable and changeable. If the first sphere is the expression of the genre, then the fourth is its modification. N. Kopystyanskaya states that in this area "the greatest modification amplitude and "elasticity" of the genre are possible" .

List of used literature:

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